

DISCURSIVE ELEMENTS AND THE CATEGORY OF POLITENESS

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the category of politeness as a central communicative category, since it is the regulator of communicative behavior that plays the most important role in ensuring and organizing harmonious communication.

Key words: gender, communicative behaviour, discourse, male, female, speech behaviour, gender linguistics

Introduction

In modern gender linguistic studies, the focus is on the analysis of various language forms, behavioral strategies in relation to the social role of men and women. At the same time, gender is considered as a social construct, a product that arises in the process of communication [4; 11], where “male” and “female” linguistic forms are separated from real men and women and are considered as “linguistic resources for constructing gender in social practice” [1: 134]. Gender studies in linguistics are based on three main models for studying male and female speech behavior: the dominance model (an explication of gender inequality in communication in accordance with the dominant social status of men) [10; 12], a deficit model (emphasizing the inferiority of the female language, considered as a deviation from the norm) [15] and a difference model (positioning the normativity of the male language and the inferiority of the female language) [18]. At the same time, the works of scientists also interpret the modern paradigm, which emphasizes the dynamics of gender differences in the language, where gender as a social category is constructed in the process of communication and is a product of discourse [14].

Materials and methods

In sociolinguistic gender studies, the attention of scientists is focused on the analysis of etiquette communication, which emphasizes that female speech behavior is aimed at establishing and developing personal relationships, in contrast to male, which is seen as a means of receiving and transmitting information [14: 3]. Women's speech behavior is defined by researchers as less categorical, including tactics of indirect influence on the addressee, such

politeness strategies as showing attention, sympathy, approval towards the interlocutor [7: 160; 18].

Given the understanding of discourse as a social practice, one can observe an analogy between the concepts of "discourse" and "style", so the stylistic analysis of speech can be interpreted as a discursive analysis. It was in the sense of "functional style" that the term discourse began to be widely used in the early 1970s. Yu. S. Stepanov speaks about this in his work. "Alternative world. Discourse, Fact and Principle of Causality" (Stepanov, 1995), believing that the main reason for replacing the term functional style with the concept of discourse lies in the Russian linguistic tradition, where functional style meant a special type of texts, while the Anglo-Saxon tradition had nothing of the kind, since there was no stylistics as a special branch of linguistics. The strategies of politeness, identified with speech etiquette, are described in linguistic studies as expressions of consent, informality and awareness, which are aimed at maintaining communication in accordance with the social roles and role positions of the interlocutors, at achieving a positive result in the communication process, at harmonious interpersonal interaction in combination with linguistic strategies, verbal means [2; 3:53; 5:139; 8:413; 17: 382-383].

Results and Discussion

According to M.Yu. Ryabova, elements of speech etiquette are present in the daily practice of any native speaker, i.e. "The specifics of speech etiquette lies in the fact that it characterizes both everyday language practice and the language norm", while the implementation of the rules of speech etiquette is determined both by the very situation of speech communication and its parameters, including the social status and relations between its participants [6 : 133].

The implementation of speech etiquette, which manifests itself in such speech strategies as reducing the categoricalness of statements, hyperbolic expression, intensifying a positive assessment, is achieved in the process of communication through the use of discursive markers and discursive elements (I mean, I think, you know, and, well, sort of, just , really, simply, absolutely). Such linguistic means, according to scientists, are more frequent in female speech and are used to share personal experience, knowledge, opinions, express consent, attention, invitation to the development of a discursive event [11; 14; 16; 23].

According to the unanimous opinion of researchers, such discursive elements as really, exactly, absolutely, just, simply, quite, performing an interpersonal function, mark the relationship, opinions, emotions of the speakers, serve as keys to the interpretation of the text, contributing to the implementation of rapprochement or distancing between the interlocutors [9; 13].

We emphasize that the use of these linguistic means in male and female speech behavior depends on the functioning of one or another element in the discourse as a means of underestimating, softening or strengthening the categoricalness of statements. Obviously, the more frequent use of discursive elements as markers of etiquette communication in women's speech behavior is confirmed by such basic characteristics of women's language as the desire for cooperation, support, mutual understanding, and interest in interpersonal communication. Let us illustrate the use of discursive elements in male and female speech of the English-language interview discourse, where these language means, pointing to the interaction, cooperation of the speakers, contribute to the observance of polite communication.

The use of the discursive element just when softening the categorical nature of interrogative statements is typical for the male speech of the interview discourse. (1) Peter Anthony Holder: As I mentioned earlier, I've always noticed your sense of fun in all the characters you've played and I was just wondering if you have any desire to do just a bang out comedy? [20] Example (2) shows the strengthening of the expression of gratitude, which refers to the stable formulas of speech etiquette, using the discursive element really, which is typical for male speech in the English-language interview discourse. (2) Larry King: Well said. Thank you both very much, John Prendergast, George Clooney. We really appreciate it. We hope every little bit helps. Thank you guys [19]. For female speech in the English discourse of the interview, the use of discursive elements is more typical with the intensification of expressions of praise, approval, consent, a positive attitude towards the interlocutor, the described situation. In such speech formulas of etiquette communication, a characteristic feature of female speech is the use of the discursive element just. The following example shows the use of the discursive just element in the amplification function when expressing praise, emphasizing the positive evaluation of the work of a famous actor. (3) J.K. Rowling: Dan is great. ... Finding Harry was very hard. ... And then the producers and director told us one night and they've found one. And Danny is an actor. I mean he's just perfect [21]. Expressions of agreement, which are also seen as emotional approvals, can be reinforced with discursive elements.

Thus, the use of the discursive element exactly in speech situations of approval of the opinions of communication partners is typical for female speech of the interview discourse. (4) O. Winfrey: Did you ever imagine your life being the way it is now? J.K. Rowling: No. never. ... I had no one near me professionally or personally who could in any way help me when I had questions like “what do you do when the press is searching your bins?” ... O. Winfrey: But that doesn't happen to most writers, you know? J.K. Rowling: Exactly. So it took everyone around me totally by surprise [22].

Conclusion

To sum up, an analysis of the use of discursive elements in male and female speech in the interview discourse showed that both male and female models of speech behavior are characterized by the use of discursive elements as markers of etiquette communication. At the same time, these linguistic means are a characteristic feature of female speech. In situations of softening the categoricalness of statements in interrogative constructions, when expressing advice, recommendations, suggestions, discursive elements contribute to maintaining distance, restraint between interlocutors. In situations of strengthening positive emotions when expressing approval, consent, praise, gratitude, discursive elements mark the manifestation of interest, goodwill, cooperation, serve to create a friendly atmosphere and maintain verbal interaction.

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